

THE ROLE OF MEDIA COMPETENCE IN FORMING SPIRITUAL MATURITY IN STUDENTS IN THE INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT

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Key words: spiritual competence, spirituality, information environment, professional spirituality, media competence, information culture, "information exhaustion syndrome", media education, media psychology.

Abstract: This article describes the formation of students' moral maturity in the information environment. The spiritual maturity of the person, the requirements for the development of the spiritual maturity of students, the development indicators of media competence of university students, media psychology and its main tasks are given. Certain recommendations have been given for the formation of the skills of spiritual maturity in the formation of the competence of students to use information correctly.

РОЛЬ МЕДИАКОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ДУХОВНОЙ ЗРЕЛОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ СРЕДЕ

Ключевые слова: духовная компетентность, духовность, информационная среда, профессиональная духовность, медиакомпетентность, информационная культура, «синдром информационного истощения», медиаобразование, медиапсихология.

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается формирование нравственной зрелости студентов в информационной среде. Приведены духовная зрелость личности, требования к развитию духовной зрелости студентов, показатели развития медиакомпетентности студентов вуза, медиапсихология и ее основные задачи. Даны определенные рекомендации по формированию навыков духовной зрелости в формировании компетентности студентов правильно использовать информацию.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the scientific research carried out on student-youth in the world, scientific research aimed at spiritual and moral education is becoming important for the formation of spiritual maturity. Therefore, the development of an interactive system for diagnosing the development of spiritual maturity in students by means of information and communication, the implementation of systematic work on the definition and achievement of strategic goals for the development of spiritual and moral worldview in students, the formation of a harmonious personality spirituality and worldview on the basis of values has become an urgent task. It should be noted that in several countries, such as the United Kingdom, Japan, the United States, France, a set of qualities inherent in a spiritually mature, harmonious personality has been developed.

In the reforms carried out in our republic, special importance is paid to creating a holistic system of spiritual and educational processes, improving organizational and research aspects of protecting young people from various information attacks in the mediamakan, effectively establishing the use of media, systematic content of students' spiritual and moral competencies (virtues), culture of working with information.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To increase the effectiveness and effectiveness of spiritual and educational work organized in higher educational institutions during the new development period of Uzbekistan, to strengthen the sense of belonging to the reforms carried out in the thinking of students and young people, to be able to use and correctly accept the database they face in the information environment, to organize the, much attention is paid to improving the effectiveness of scientific and methodological research in this area.

3. LIST OF THEMATIC LITERATURE

M. from scientists of the Republic. Kakharova[1], G. Makhmutova[2], N. Norqulova[3], Z. Salieva[4], Sh. Taylakova[5], U. Utanov[6], M. Raising the spiritual potential of students in the research of quranovs[7], developing the quality of enlightenment in students and young people, forming pedagogical culture in students in the process of teaching Pedagogical Sciences, ensuring the stability of the spiritual and moral environment in society, education of the qualities of etiquette in students studying in higher educational institutions on the basis of national spiritual heritage, the issues of social pedagogical features of the formation of spiritual maturity of students,

improvement of pedagogical mechanisms for the development of spiritual culture, formation of the spiritually mature personality image of students, cultural, personal and professional socialization of students are highlighted.

L. from scientists of the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS).Suprunova[8], S.Troyanskaya[9], Ye.Shiyanov[10], G.Shevelyova [11] S determine the composition of the competencies of graduates of Higher Education, the spiritual and moral formation of students in the pedagogical culture system, pedagogical factors of the spiritual and moral formation of the individual in the educational process are studied.

K. from foreign scientists.Anderson[12], M.Anthony[13], N.Alt[14], V.Lesniak[15], P.Prospers for Spiritual Formation, a system of continuous spiritual development throughout life, a psychological and integrative model of spiritual formation have been studied, among others, Howard[16].

It is appropriate to explain the importance of the development of an Information Service System in the educational system, as well as in other areas, by the fact that it directly applies to improving the effectiveness of the educational process. When Information Service and supply is not at the level of demand, no matter what type and aspect of the educational system, it will certainly negatively affect the educational process, leading to a decrease in the quality of Education. This, in turn, also causes a violation of the optimization of the information supply. As a result, it leads to the derailment of all organizational and pedagogical, psychological, economic activities related to the education system, the solution of cultural and educational, creative issues, the training of highly qualified specialists. In this sense, the scientific-theoretical justification of the optimal option of Information System and supply in the educational system is one of the pressing issues of today.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The requirements for the development of the level of spiritual maturation of students are established:

- Formation of feelings of striving for perfection in the BKM;
- Nurture feelings of aspiration towards spiritual maturity in BKM;
- To achieve the implementation of information on subjects and related information in the educational program in the preparation of BKM through the regular use of the timed press;

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- To achieve effective use of information and resource centers in the regular acquaintance of BKM with new fiction and professional literature;
- implementation of the training of future junior specialists brought up by professional spirituality, spiritual and moral aspects;
- interest in developing a perfect plan for organizing mass-educational events on spiritual and educational work and creating innovative methods of their conduct;
- to have personal qualities with high spirituality.

During our research, we also want to dwell on the inherent importance of mediacompetency in the formation of spiritual maturity in students. Media gives the meaning that in Latin is a tool, standing in the middle. It is a means of meeting spiritual (information, knowledge) needs. An unbiased tool like a knife, fire, water. The knife in the doctor's hand sucks the patient. The knife in the offender's hand makes sigh sick. When the light of the fire freezes a person, most of them burn. If a lot of water is drowned, then the waterlessness will crumble. So is the Media. If in moderation, competently used, then for media sages-a source of knowledge. For fools-the source of troubles[17,18]. So it turns out that the point is not in the media, but in those who use it, or rather – every guy-girl depends on her mediumship.

Shablin M.S. pedagogical technology for the formation of mediacompetence of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions by means of animated composition has been developed, substantiated and tested experimentally. This technology provides a leading place for the interaction of the United arts with a common goal and result, consisting in the creation of animated composition, the introduction of colorful types of visual and technical activities that develop the creative potential of students of pedagogical higher education institutions, the use of a special system of assignments and exercises[19].

Myasnikova T.I. in his research work "the development of mediacompetency of university students", he noted that mediacompetence is the result of personal-subjective acquisition of a (characterizing) student in the process of formal and informal education, which characterizes the individual's individual (individual) readiness for communication with media. [20]

Mediapsychology is a new, dynamically developing field of Psychological Science, the subject of which is a person considered in the context of modern

mediamadanism as a dynamically developing field of World Culture. The main tasks of mediapsychology include:

- study of individual and media-influenced behavior of the individual;
- individual and group mediaeffects research iqlish;
- analysis of the influence of mediamuhit on the development of the subject, the recovery of the individual and the psychological self-perception of a person;
- development of programs for the formation of mediahimodality and mediacompetency of the individual.

Another leading Russian media scholar is Fedorov A.V. In his monograph "development of mediacompetence and critical thinking of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions" [21], issues of development of mediacompetency and critical thinking of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions (within the framework of the specialty "Mediata'lim", state registration number No. 03.13.30) were studied in the context of general problems of mediata education and mediasavodkhanate.

Taking into account the above points, it can be noted that, in our opinion, the most convenient way to develop the mediacompetency of students of pedagogical higher education institutions is to develop the course "Informatics and Information Technology" in the process of teaching information technology, multimedia – technologies. Special courses on Multimedia foundations, aimed at increasing the level of mediacompetence, in our opinion, allow graduates to demonstrate a high level of mediacompetency not only in education in a higher educational institution, but also in subsequent professional pedagogical activity.

These courses should be built on the basis of principles that provide the opportunity to organize an educational environment that promotes work methods, cognitive independence, interest in research activities, development of group work skills, self-control and increased responsibility for continuing education in the field of multimedia-technology use. In doing so, students gain mediacompetency through the acquisition, development and improvement of information and communication technologies.

In short, the future of the implementation of the above tasks also depends on the wishes, character of the teacher and his professional training. If a person is not afraid

of changes, moving forward with a bold step in New conditions, he will achieve the set goal in short periods of time.

5. CONCLUSION

1. It should be noted that the formation of spiritual maturity in the conditions of the information environment of students is an urgent problem, in particular, a separate study of the problem of better application of knowledge on spiritual maturity, identification of achievements and shortcomings in this area, promising directions and their research.

2. In the conditions of education and upbringing, it is necessary to take into account the age, psychological characteristics of students;

3. In the content of the competence of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions on media, the following interconnected elements were identified: (a) literacy in media; (b) readiness to demonstrate their motivation for media knowledge. To further develop "mediacompetence", it is a period requirement to use the experiences of developed countries, to include disciplines that illuminate the concepts of mediacompetence in educational plans, and to create methodological manuals that illuminate the concepts of mediacompetence.

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